

**The Effect of Molecule Structure of Proteolytic Enzymes in Mangoes, Kiwi, Pear,
Pineapple, and Papaya Leaves on the Effectiveness of Protein Coagulation and Meat
Tenderization**

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Abstract

This study was conducted to investigate the effects of structural molecules of proteolytic enzymes found in mangoes, kiwifruits, pears, pineapples, and papaya leaves. The use of natural proteolytic enzymes, such as those from papaya leaves and pineapples, to tenderize meat is still prevalent in many countries, particularly in Indonesia. In this experiment, we utilized natural proteolytic enzymes from other types of fruits, namely mangoes, kiwi, and pears, which possess specific proteolytic enzymes with distinct molecular formulas.

The first step in testing for proteolytic enzymes involved the use of protein coagulation methods. Extracted samples were added to Greenfields fresh pasteurized milk, allowed to sit for 30 minutes, and the time required for the milk protein to denature was recorded.

The second part of the study aimed to investigate the effectiveness of these enzymes in tenderizing meat. We prepared extracted samples with concentrations of 0%, 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% in aquadest, and coated them onto the meat, and then observed changes over 30, 60, and 90 minutes. The hardness of the meat was assessed annually. The experiment showed that papaya leaves were the most effective at tenderizing the meat.

Keywords : enzyme, structure molecule, proteolytic enzymes, serine, actinidin, cysteine, bromelain, papain, protein coagulation, meat tenderization, natural enzymes.

Introduction

Enzymes are biological catalysts that can accelerate specific chemical reactions and are also typically proteins. One enzyme of particular interest is proteolytic enzymes. Proteolytic enzymes catalyze the breakdown of proteins into amino acids or smaller polypeptides by hydrolyzing peptide bonds. These enzymes are categorized into two groups: exopeptidases and endopeptidases. Exopeptidases catalyze reactions at the terminal peptide bonds, while endopeptidases catalyze reactions at internal peptide bonds.

Mangoes (*Mangifera indica*), kiwi (*Actinidia deliciosa*), pears (*Pyrus nivalis*), pineapples (*Ananas comosus* L.), and papayas (*Carica papaya* L.) are not only known for their taste but also serve as natural sources of proteolytic enzymes.

Enzymes play a crucial role in various biochemical processes, particularly reactions related to protein coagulation and meat tenderization. The structures of molecules of these enzymes significantly influence their functionality as proteolytic enzymes

Each enzyme possesses a distinct chemical structure. Serine enzymes, extracted from mangoes, exhibit a molecular formula of $C_3H_7NO_3$. Actinidin enzymes, derived from kiwi fruit, possess the molecular formula $C_{10}H_{13}N$. Cysteine enzymes, obtained from pears, have the molecular formula $C_3H_7NO_2S$. Bromelain enzymes, extracted from pineapples, bear the molecular composition $C_{39}H_{66}N_2O_{29}$. Papain enzymes, extracted from papaya leaves, display the molecular structure $C_{19}H_{29}N_7O_6$.

Proteolytic enzymes, such as proteases and peptidases, play a vital role as

catalysts in the breakdown of proteins into smaller peptides and amino acids. Beyond their functions in digestion and metabolic processes, this study aims to investigate the impact of the molecule structure of each proteolytic enzyme in mangoes, kiwi, pears, pineapples, and papaya leaves on their ability to coagulate proteins and tenderize meat.

A previous study revealed the following optimum conditions for enzymes: serine enzymes exhibited optimal activity within a pH range of 7 to 11, actinidin enzymes at a pH range of 6 to 8, cysteine enzymes within a pH range of 5 to 8, bromelain enzymes at a pH range of 6.5 to 7.5, and papain enzymes at a pH range of 4.5 to 6.6. Regarding temperature, the optimal temperature ranges were as follows: serine enzymes operated best when at temperatures between 45°C and 50°C, actinidin enzymes at 35°C to 40°C, cysteine

enzymes within the range of 40°C to 70°C, bromelain enzymes at 30°C to 40°C, and papain enzymes at temperatures between 50°C and 55°C

This study aims to investigate the influence of molecular structure on the effectiveness of protein coagulation. Enzymes in this study are extracted from mangoes (serine), kiwi (actinidin), pears (cysteine), pineapples (bromelain), and papaya leaves (papain) and are tested in a phosphate buffer saline (PBS) at pH 7.4. The enzymes extracted are then added to pasteurized milk at a temperature of 40°C, and the time required for the enzymes to denature the milk protein is recorded.

The second part of our investigation focuses on examining the influence of enzymes on the tenderization of meat. To do so, place pieces of meat into enzyme solutions with concentrations of 0%, 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100%, all prepared in

distilled water (aquadest). These meat samples are allowed to soak in their respective solutions for precisely 30, 60, and 90 minutes. After the 90 minutes is complete, the meat pieces are carefully removed and subjected to a 60-minute boiling process at 80 degrees Celsius. Once that step is complete, a meticulous visual assessment is performed to evaluate and compare the degree of tenderness achieved by each meat sample.

Research Question

Does the molecule structure affect the enzyme activities of mangoes, kiwi, pear, pineapple, and papaya leaves to coagulate the protein and tenderize meat ?

Materials and Methods

Equipment Digital balance, test tubes, 1ml pipette, 10 ml pipette, measuring cylinder, beaker, ziplock bags, thermometer,

stopwatch, water bath, pH indicator, electric blender, and tweezers (forceps).

Chemicals and Plant Materials

Phosphate buffer saline (PBS) pH 7.4 from Merck, papaya leaves (*Carica papaya* L.), pineapples (*Ananas comosus* L.), kiwi (*Actinidia deliciosa*), pears (*Pyrus nivalis*), mangoes (*Mangifera Indica*), Greenfields fresh pasteurized milk, and beef.

Proteolytic enzymes extraction

Mangoes, kiwi, pears, pineapples, and papaya leaves were first washed and then sliced into thin pieces. These slices were then blended with Phosphate buffer saline (PBS) in a 1:3 ratio. The resulting mixture was filtered, and the filtrate was collected.

Protein coagulation In a test tube, 9 ml of Greenfields fresh pasteurized milk was combined with 1 ml of extract. The mixture was placed in a water bath, maintaining a temperature of approximately 40 degrees Celsius for 30 minutes. The time required for each extract to induce protein precipitation was recorded.

In order to establish a comprehensive understanding of the experiment's outcomes, a comparative analysis was conducted, comparing the results obtained with those of the control group. Furthermore, the pH levels of the solutions were examined both before and after the protein had settled. To ensure the accuracy and reliability of the results, this experiment was repeated three times.

Meat Tenderization The meat was cut into 30-gram square pieces and subsequently soaked in enzyme extracts prepared at concentrations of 0%, 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100%. The meat was left in these solutions for 30, 60, and 90 minutes. Afterwards, the meat was then boiled for 60 minutes at 80 degrees Celsius, and its tenderness was assessed visually.

Results and Discussion

Extract	Mango	Kiwi	Pear	Pineapple	Papaya Leaves
Time (minutes)	>30	27	>30	12	15

Table 1. Time taken for protein extracts to coagulate milk

The results showed that pineapple extract coagulated protein in the shortest time. Pineapple took 12 minutes to coagulate milk protein, while papaya leaves required 15 minutes, kiwi needed 27 minutes, and mangoes and pears did not produce any changes even after 30 minutes.

Furthermore, when the mango and pear extracts were left for one hour, there were still no changes in the milk protein.

Fig. 1. Protein coagulation with pineapple extract.

Fig. 2. Protein coagulation with Papaya leaves extract.

Fig. 3. Protein coagulation with kiwi extract.

Fig. 4. Protein coagulation with mangoes extract

Fig. 5. Protein coagulation with pears extract

Meat tenderization

The experiment showed that papaya leaves were the most effective at tenderizing the meat.

Fruit	Hardness (out of 10)			
	25%	50%	75%	100%
Kiwi	10	8	8	6.5
Pineapple	8	7.5	7.5	5
Papaya Leaves	6	6	5.5	3
Mangoes	9.5	9	9.5	9.5
Pears	9.5	9	9.5	9
Control : 9/10				

Table 2. Hardness of meat after soaked in enzymes extract with concentration 0%, 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100%.

The result showed that papaya leaves have the smallest hardness (check manually). From table 1, the order of enzyme activities from the strongest to the weakest to tenderize meat is papaya leaves, pineapple, kiwi, pear, and mango.

Discussion

Structure molecules have a significant effect on the effectiveness of protein coagulation or protein denaturation. Protein coagulation occurs when the native protein is disrupted, leading to a change in its three-dimensional conformation.

Milk contains various proteins, with the two main types being casein and whey proteins. Casein is the primary protein involved in milk coagulation. Papain cleaves the peptide bonds within the casein molecules, leading to the formation of smaller peptide fragments. As papain continues to cleave the peptide bonds, the smaller casein fragments start to aggregate

and bind together. This aggregation forms a gel-like structure, which traps fat and water, leading to the coagulation or thickening of the milk.

Bromelain is a mixture of proteolytic enzymes, including cysteine proteases, which can break peptide bonds in proteins. These enzymes cleave the peptide bonds within the protein molecules. As bromelain breaks down the peptide bonds, it can cause the denaturation of the protein molecules. Denaturation involves the unfolding and disruption of the protein's native structure.

Mangoes contain many enzymes, but only few contain proteolytic enzymes. The primary enzymes found in mangoes are amylases and pectinases, which are involved in the breakdown of carbohydrates and pectin. That's way, mangoes extract doesn't give positive results in protein coagulation. Same as mangoes, Pears do not contain

significant amounts of proteolytic enzymes like papain or bromelain.

Actinidin enzymes from kiwi contain proteolytic enzymes similar to papain and bromelain. However, their effect on protein coagulation is weaker compared to papain and bromelain.

From both the experiment and the literature, it's evident that proteolytic enzymes from mangoes and pears are the weakest in their effect, possibly due to their molecular structure. Bromelain, papain, and actinidin have specific molecular structures that allow them to break down protein bonds and alter the three-dimensional conformation.

For meat tenderization, papaya leaves are the most effective due to the presence of papain enzymes. The results differ somewhat from those of protein coagulation. Protein in milk has different amino acid composition. Milk contains

various kinds of protein, but two main proteins are casein and whey protein.

Meat contains proteins, with the main proteins being myoglobin and actin. Myoglobin is a protein responsible for providing a red color and has the function of storing oxygen. Actin is a protein involved in muscle contractions. The difference of protein present causes the results to be different.

Conclusion

The molecular structures have affected the enzyme activities of mangoes, kiwi, pear, pineapple, and papaya leaves in their ability to coagulate milk protein and tenderize meat.

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